

EFFECT OF SONG-BASED INSTRUCTIONAL STRATEGY ON PRIMARY SCHOOL PUPILS' ACHIEVEMENT IN ENGLISH STUDIES IN AWKA SOUTH LOCAL GOVERNMENT EDUCATION AUTHORITY

¹Mbachi Roseline Anurika, ²Okonkwo, Ogechukwu Jane & ³Okoye, Chinwe Regina

^{1&2}Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka.

³Department of Educational Management and Policy, Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka
¹ra.mbaci@unizik.edu.ng, ²oj.okonkwo@unizik.edu.ng & ³okoyeregina76@gmail.com

Abstract

The study investigated the effect of song-based instructional strategy on primary school pupils' achievement in English Studies in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Two research questions guided the study and two null hypotheses tested at 0.05 level of significance guided the study. The study adopted a quasi-experimental pre-test post-test nonrandomized control group design. The population of the study comprised all the pupils in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Multistage sampling procedure was used to draw a sample size of 87 pupils for the study. English Studies Achievement Test (ESAT) containing 30 multiple choice questions was used to collect data on students' academic achievement in Mathematics. The validation of ESAT and lesson plans were established by three experts, two from Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and one from Department of Education Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation unit), all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Kuder-Richardson Formula 20 was used to establish a reliability of ESAT which yielded coefficient of 0.83. Mean and standard deviation were used to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance was used to test the hypotheses. The findings of the revealed among others that pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method. It was also found that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Based on the findings of the study, it was recommended among others that Anambra State Universal Basic Education Board should organize annual training programmes for English Studies teachers to improve their knowledge and skills of using song-based instructional strategy in teaching.

Keywords: Song-Based, Instructional Strategy, Pupils, Achievement, English Studies, Gender

Introduction

English Studies is one of the major subjects in basic education curriculum in Nigeria. The knowledge of English studies enables pupils to attain academic excellence because other subjects in basic schools are taught and written in the language. Amosun, Ajayi Ogunniyi and Oduolowu (2024) noted that English studies is one of the core subjects in primary school as well as serving as medium of instruction in the primary level of education. Amosun et al added that it is important because without a good grasp and knowledge in English studies, instructional exchanges and understanding of other subjects which are usually taught in English language will not be possible. In the same vein, Ikwuka, Nwigwe, and Ekeh (2025) opined that it imperative for all learners to be competent and proficient in English studies especially the grammar aspect of it, because deficiency in it will result to poor achievement not only in the subject itself; but also in other subjects that are taught and written in the language. Therefore, the knowledge of pupils in English Studies could influence their academic achievement in all subjects at basic education level.

Academic achievement is the learning outcomes which are often measured through the scores or grade obtained by pupils from continuous assessment and examinations. According to Okoli, Anyachebelu and Enemu (2024), academic achievement is the learning outcome which indicates the level of mastery, proficiency and knowledge shown by an individual after learning has taken place. Academic achievement is criteria of determining success and progress of pupils in their educational pursuit, Academic achievement is described by Nwaubani, Anyachebelu and Chigbo-Obasi (2023), scores obtained by pupils in an evaluation exercise given to test their knowledge of classroom subject in primary schools. Furthermore, Nwaubani et al asserted that academic achievement is the measurement of the mental level of pupils on subjects enrolled at the end of the term or academic session in primary school. Academic achievement usually show the progress made by pupils towards accomplishing instructional goals in education institutions. Okafor and Aniebo (2020) noted that academic achievement is one of the means of determining the level of attainment specific goals of learning in educational institutions. Nnalue, Nnorom and Christian-Ike (2021) described academic achievement as the sum of the scores obtained by learners in a given test or examination. Academic achievement is the learning outcomes that reflect the knowledge acquired by pupils who are taught in educational institutions.

The academic achievement in English Studies of pupils is still below expectations in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Okigbo and Okeke (2021) noted that the summary of pupils' performance in first school leaving certificate (FSLC) examination over the period of four years from 2014 to 2017 as documented by Examination Development Centre Awka, Anambra state revealed that, out of 280,596 pupils that sat for FSLC examination over the period of four years, only 114,117(40.69%) had credit pass and above in English Language and Mathematics, while the remaining 166,419 (59.31 %) had pass and below. In the same vein, Basic Education Certificate Examination Chief Examiners report cited in Ikebuaso and Obumneke-Okeke (2020) revealed that the Basic Education Certificate Examination analysis released for 2014 and 2015 academic year show that pupils from Anambra State have 40 percent average in English language. In 2016, 2017 and 2018, the results were worse, as pupils have 30 percent average in English language. The academic achievement which is often below expectations could be associated with conventional method of teaching the subject.

Conventional teaching method is an approach to lesson presentation through discussion, explanation and demonstration of ideas to pupils to observe, make contributions

and ask questions. According to Anyachebelu and Nnebuo (2020), conventional method of teaching is an oral presentation of information to pupils with little or no active involvement or effort on the part of the pupil. Conventional teaching method which has potentials of negative impacts on pupils' academic achievement in English Studies is still used widely in teaching pupils in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Amosun et al (2024) defined conventional teaching method as the teacher-centred method in which learners receive information from the teacher to the detriment of engagement in instructional activities in the classroom. Teachers who apply conventional teaching method reliance on lesson plan and note, textbooks and worksheets to deliver instruction to pupils. Observation has shown that conventional teaching method, make pupils to become passive learners which are probably parts of the main reasons behind their low achievement in English Studies in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. On the ways to make pupils to become active learner is the song-based instructional strategy.

Song-based instructional strategy is the use of rhymes in teaching learners in the classroom. Hilot and Dioso (2024) described song-based instructional strategy as the approach of teaching through meaningful combinations of sounds conveyed through the use of rhythm, melody, and harmony which are performed using voices. Continug, Hilot and Dioso stressed that incorporating song into instruction can enhance learners' engagement and foster greater interaction among peers in the classroom. It involves short musical composition with lyrics describing content of lessons presented to pupils in the classroom. Undie, Ibok, Okon and Ani (2024) described song based instructional strategy as the use of song as a method of teaching in classroom which is capable of enhancing the whole child development in term of intellectual, social, emotional, physical and creativity. It entails singing song that related to the content of English Studies to aid pupils' understanding and retention of the subject matters. Activity-Based instructional strategy is described by Mustapha, Gana, Waziri, Bukar and Buba (2020), as a teaching method adopted by an instructor to ensure that learner is actively engaged mentally and physically. Continuing, Mustapha et al asserted that this approach is based on the core premise that learning should be based on doing some hands-on experiments and activities rather than just listening to lessons. The use of song-based instructional strategy stimulates the attention of pupils and removes boredom in the teaching-learning processes in the classroom.

The use of song-based instructional strategy creates a relaxed, fun and enjoyable atmosphere that encourage active participation of pupils in learning English Language. Tahani, Mosaddaq and Jamal (2021) asserted that some of the essential aspects of song-based instructional strategy are that they are enjoyable and can keep students excited. Furthermore, Tahani et al averred that the use of song-based instructional strategy has potentials of improving listening ability, rhythm and pronunciation, and provide a fun atmosphere. The use of song-based instructional strategy in teaching English Studies can improve the speaking and pronunciation skills of pupils. Omollo and Massam (2022) marinated that the use of song-based instructional strategy can transform learners from their passive states to active ones during teaching and activities in the classroom.

Gender is behavioural patterns, social identity and cultural roles associated with being males and females. Okafor, Ughamadu and Enwezor (2024) defined gender as the patterns of behaviour, roles and expectations associated with being males or females. Gender comparison in pupils' academic achievement taught using song-based instructional strategy have been examined for some time resulting in substantial empirical studies with varying results. Undie, Ibok, Okon and Ani (2024) male pupils who were taught using song based instructional strategy performed better than their female counterpart who were taught with the

same treatment. On the other hand, Salami and Owolabi (2015) which revealed there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores in male and female learners taught using song-based instructional strategy. The need arises for further studies to take gender into consideration to examine effect of song-based instructional strategy on primary school pupils' achievement in English Studies in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to determine effect of song-based instructional strategy on primary school pupils' achievement in English Studies in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Specifically, the study seeks to determine:

1. Mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.
2. Mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

1. What are the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?
2. What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?

Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

1. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.
2. There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Methods

A quasi-experimental design, specifically a pretest posttest non-equivalent control group design was adopted for the study. The study was carried out in Awka South Local Government Education Authority, Anambra State. The population of the study comprised all the basic five pupils in basic schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. The sample size for this study was 87 pupils from two coeducational basic schools using multistage sampling procedure. In the first stage, purposive sampling technique was used to select co-educational schools with qualified teachers and essential facilities. In the second stage, simple random sampling (balloting with replacement) was used to draw two intact classes from the two selected basic schools. One intact class in one of the sampled schools was assigned to experimental group while the other in another sampled school was randomly assigned to control group. This assignment into groups was done using a flip of the coin.

Experimental class (Group A) consists of 41 pupils (18 males and 23 females) and control class (Group B) consists of 46 pupils (20 males and 26 females).

The instrument for data collection was English Studies Achievement Test (EAAT). The items in the instrument were adapted and re-organized by the researcher from past common entrance question papers. The EAAT consisted of two sections, A and B. Section A consists of pupils' bio data such as gender, while section B had 30-item multiple choice questions with four options of A-D. The instrument (EAAT) was validated by three experts, two from the Department of Early Childhood and Primary Education and one from Department of Educational Foundations (Measurement and Evaluation unit), all from Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The reliability of the instrument was determined using Richardson Formula 20 ($K - R 20$) which yielded coefficient of 0.83.

English Language teachers of each intact class were trained to serve as the research assistants. The trained class teachers administered the pre-test (ESAT) to pupils to determine the extent of their knowledge of concepts to be taught in English Studies before the experiment. The experimental group was taught using SBIS, while the control group was taught using CTM. At the end of the treatment, post-tests were administered using the same ESAT which was reshuffled. Data collected were analysed using mean and standard deviation to answer the research questions and Analysis of Covariance (ANCOVA) to test the hypotheses. The decision rule for the hypotheses is that whenever the probability value (p-value) is less than or equal to the significant value of 0.05, the null hypothesis was rejected, otherwise the null hypothesis was not rejected.

Results

Research Question 1: What are the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?

Table 1: Mean Pre-test and Posttest Achievement Scores of Pupils Taught English Studies Using Song-Based Instructional Strategy and that of those Taught Using Conventional Teaching Method

Method	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
SBIS	41	13.11	26.04	4.39	2.03	12.93
CTM	46	12.93	17.12	6.01	3.11	4.19

Table 1 shows that pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had pre-test achievement mean score of 13.11 with standard deviation of 4.39, while their posttest mean achievement score was 26.04 with 2.03 value of standard deviation and mean gain of 12.93. The pupils taught English Studies using conventional teaching method had pre-test achievement mean score of 12.93 with standard deviation of 6.01, while their posttest mean achievement score was 17.12 with 3.11 value of standard deviation and 4.19 mean gain.

The mean achievement gain difference between pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and those taught using the conventional teaching method was 8.74 in favour of the experimental group. The spread of score in the posttest is more homogenous among pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy because the SD scores is smaller (2.09) compared to the SD score (3.11) of those taught using

conventional teaching method. The result indicated that pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method.

Research Question 2: What are the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority?

Table 2: Mean Pre-test and Posttest Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils Taught English Studies Using Song-Based Instructional Strategy

Gender	N	Pretest Mean	Posttest Mean	Pretest SD	Posttest SD	Mean Gain
Male	18	12.05	24.89	4.75	1.99	12.84
Female	23	14.18	25.66	4.22	2.03	11.48

Result in Table 2 shows that male pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had pre-test achievement mean score of 12.05 with standard deviation of 4.75, while their posttest mean achievement score was 24.89 with 1.09 value of standard deviation and mean gain of 12.84. On the other hand, female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had pre-test achievement mean score of 14.18 with standard deviation of 4.22, while their posttest mean achievement score was 25.66 with 2.03 value of standard deviation and 11.48 mean gain.

The mean achievement gain difference between male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy was 1.36 in favour of the experimental group. The spread of score in the posttest is more homogenous among male pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy because the SD scores is smaller (1.99) compared to the SD score (2.03) of their female counterparts. The result indicated that male pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had slightly higher achievement score than their female counterparts.

Hypothesis 1: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Table 3: Summary of ANCOVA on Difference between the Mean Achievement Scores of Pupils Taught English Studies Using Song-Based Instructional Strategy and that of those Taught Using Conventional Teaching Method

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	4530.194	2	2265.097	168.349	.000	
Intercept	1455.336	1	1455.336	143.227	.000	
Pretest	549.109	1	549.109	24.654	.000	
Method	5096.098	1	5096.098	332.543	.000	S
Error	909.536	86	10.576			
Total	6908.128	89				
Corrected Total	4675.544	85				

a. R Square = .733 (Adjusted R Square = .730)

As shown in Table 3, at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 86df denominator, the calculated F is 332.543 with P-value of .000 which is less than 0.05. Thus,

the null hypothesis was rejected. Therefore, there is significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Hypothesis 2: There is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Table 4: Summary of ANCOVA on Difference between the Mean Achievement Scores of Male and Female Pupils Taught English Studies Using Song-Based Instructional Strategy

Source of variation	SS	Df	MS	F	P-value	Decision
Corrected Model	4227.130	2	2113.565	125.332	.000	
Intercept	1367.356	1	1367.356	133.654	.020	
Pretest	370.487	1	370.487	30.122	.010	
Gender	5087.234	1	5087.234	453.209	.032	S
Error	765.142	86	8.897			
Total	6432.876	89				
Corrected Total	4321.768	87				

b. R Square = .825 (Adjusted R Square = .822)

It is shown in Table 4 that at 0.05 level of significance, 1df numerator and 87df denominator, the F-ratio is 453.209 with P-value of 0.32 which is greater than 0.05. Thus, the null hypothesis was not rejected. Therefore, there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Discussion

The finding of the study revealed that pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had higher achievement score than those taught using conventional teaching method. This agreed with the finding of Undie, Ibok, Okon and Ani (2024) which showed that primary school pupils who were taught using the song based instructional strategy had higher academic achievement than those taught using conventional teaching method. The agreement between the findings could be attributed to similarity in time span and country in which the studies were conducted. The possible explanation for this finding is that song-based instructional strategy promotes learning in active participation which improve retention level of pupils, unlike the conventional teaching method which promote passive learning. Song-based instructional strategy caters for different learning styles of pupils which could account for the high achievement scores than those taught using conventional teaching method. Further result indicated that there is significant difference between the mean achievement scores of pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy and that of those taught using conventional teaching method in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. This upheld the finding of Undie, Ibok, Okon and Ani (2024) which revealed that there is a significant difference between the mean achievement scores of primary school pupils who were taught using the using song based instructional strategy and those taught using conventional teaching method. This disagreed with the finding of Hilot and Dioso (2024) which showed that there was a significant disparity in the mean scores between learners taught using activity-based

instructional strategy and those taught using expository teaching method, with the experimental group achieving a superior outcome. The difference in geographical location can contribute to the disagreement between the findings.

The result of the study revealed that that male pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy had slightly higher achievement score than their female counterparts. This is in agreement with the finding of Undie, Ibok, Okon and Ani (2024) which showed that male pupils who were taught using song based instructional strategy performed better than their female counterparts who were taught with the same treatment. Song-based instructional strategy might be the preferred learning style of male pupils which could make them attain slightly greater achievement than their female counterparts in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. It was also found that there is no significant difference between the mean achievement scores of male and female pupils taught English Studies using song-based instructional strategy in primary schools Awka South Local Government Education Authority. This affirmed the finding of Salami and Owolabi (2015) which revealed there was no significant difference in the mean achievement scores in male and female learners taught using song-based instructional strategy. Song-based instructional strategy provide equal opportunities for both male and female pupils to actively participate in the teaching and learning process to improve their academic achievement in Mathematics.

Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that of song-based instructional strategy is a way of teaching English Studies in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority. Song-based instructional strategy is superior to the convention method of teaching English Studies in primary schools in Awka South Local Government Education Authority.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the following recommendations were made:

1. English Studies teachers should integrate song-based instructional strategy in teaching.
2. Anambra State Universal Basic Education Board should organize annual training programmes for English Studies teachers to improve their knowledge and skills of using song-based instructional strategy in teaching.

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